

Economic Empowerment Of Educable Intellectually Disabled Children (EIDC) In Special Schools Of West Bengal

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Economic empowerment is a very important part of our life. We must engage in any occupation, job, or vocational work for economic support. Here an attempt has been made to explore the Economic Empowerment of Educable Intellectually Disabled Children (EIDC) in Special Schools in West Bengal. Data are collected through interviews by teleconferencing with a self-made open-ended questionnaire from special educators. Ten special schools from five districts of West Bengal, namely Bankura, Hooghly, Kolkata, North, and South 24 Parganas are randomly selected. Ten special educators were purposively selected from those special schools. Bakery products, chocolates, tea, glass printing, tablemats, Jutes items, candles, making rakhis, kurti, salwaretc, oxide jewelry, soft toys, paper packets, envelopes, etc. are the products for which proper training is being given in these special schools. These products are sold in school exhibitions, local markets, and different fairs with the help of parents and school authorities. They get portions of cash from the earned money and also get a job in their school or a clerical post or staff in any shopping mall. So, more opportunities are needed to be created to make them economically independent or empowered, more facilities from government, more involvement of parents and awareness in the society, can bring more jobs and economic empowerment for EIDC.

Keywords: Economic Empowerment, Educable Intellectually Disabled Children (EIDC), Special Educator.

Empowerment is a term about language and the politics of human services as cited by Lord and Hutchison (1993). Empowerment refers to power, financial support or economic

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ECONOMIC EMPOWERMENT OF EIDC IN SPECIAL SCHOOLS

empowerment that gives everyone an identity & dignity in society. Economic empowerment refers to the ability to make and act on decisions involving controlling and allocating financial resources. As human beings, we all need financial support to run our lives. The RPWD Act, 2016 (Ministry of Law and Justice, Govt. of India, 2016) listed 21 disabilities, including ID or Intellectually Disabled Children. Based on the IQ range, the classification of Intellectual Disabilities is Mild, Moderate, Severe, Profound, and others. According to educational classification of Intellectual Disabilities, the classification is Educable, Trainable, and Custodial. The term EIDC, or Educable Intellectually Disabled Children, refers to Mild & Moderate ID children whose IQ range is 35/36 to 70/75. If they are given proper training, they can be independent in their functional life.

Mishra (2021) did a study to analyse the empowerment of persons with disabilities in India & indicated that a number of policies have been formed but the problem is with their implementation. Indrasari, Riyadi, and Purnomo (2019) conducted a review on implementation of the Empowerment Programs for Persons with Disabilities in Indonesia to find out different types of programs to empower them in Indonesia. Niesz, Koch and Rumrill (2008) conducted a study on economic empowerment through vocational training rehabilitation. Thomas and Thomas (2005) found out that Self-Help Groups can ensure better access to existing schemes and programs and becomes a tool for the overall empowerment of persons with disability.

METHOD

Sample

Ten special schools from five districts of West Bengal, namely Bankura, Hooghly, Kolkata, North, and South 24 Pargana were selected randomly. In addition, ten special educators were purposively selected from these schools. Data was collected through interviews by teleconferencing with a self-made open-ended questionnaire. Coding and categorizing are done from the Transcribed data.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

For a better qualitative understanding of data, ten categories are shaped based on the codes illustrated below:

Derived codes and categories from the data analysis

Codes	Categories with numbers
Instructions Interested Motivated Work Enjoyment	C:1 Active Participations

TAPASI BISWAS AND BISWAJIT CHATTERJEE

Providing Raw Materials Providing Machines Fulfilling the Market's Demands Parent's Help	C:2 Role of Schools
Foods Items Art-craft Materials Home Decorating Objects Festival Items Dress and Jewellery Items Toys Paper Items	C:3 Products Making
School Exhibitions Different Fair Local Markets Selling by Parents	C:4 Products Selling
Earning Cash Money Bank Transferring Organising a One-day Trip Buying Raw Materials	C:5 Using of Earn Money
NRI Funds Higher Authority's Funds State Funds Central Government Funds	C:6 Arrangement of Funds
Office Clerk Shopping Mall Staffs Own Business	C:7 Job Placements
Interested Motivated Lack of Awareness Lack of Involvement	C:8 Parent's Participation
Feeling Energetic Interested Feeling Anger	C:9 Trainer's Participations
Wants Governmental Facilities Focusing on individuality Necessities of Job Findings Needs Awareness Parental Counseling	C:10 Special Educator's Suggestions

ECONOMIC EMPOWERMENT OF EIDC IN SPECIAL SCHOOLS

C:1 Active Participation: Active participation of EIDC, in particular work or training, is a step towards economic empowerment. This category was developed based on the codes 'Instructions', 'Interested', 'Motivated', and 'Work Enjoyment'. Maximum collected data proved that the EIDC tried to actively participate in their training by following all instructions of trainers, parents, or school authorities. They were interested and motivated in their work or training, such as financial support & other rewards encouraged them, and they enjoyed their work.

C:2 Role of Schools: The category 'Role of Schools' consisted of four codes: 'Providing Raw materials', 'Providing Machines', 'Fulfilling Market's Demands', and 'Parent's Help'. All the schools arranged the raw materials and machines for making their products, and school authorities were connected with the local market for selling products.

C:3 Products Making: The category 'Products Making' is converted from these seven coding as 'Foods Items', 'Art-craft Materials', 'Home Decorating Objects', 'Festival Items', 'Dress and Jewelry Items', 'Toys', and 'Paper Items'. Since the training is for the EIDC, it needs to be easy and repetitive in nature. Bakery, chocolate, tea, etc., were prepared as food items, glass printing, tablemats, Jutes items, etc., made as home decorating items, for festivals purpose they prepared candles, rakhis, etc., in the dress and jewellery items they make kurti, salwar, oxide Jewellery etc. They also make soft toys, paper packets, envelopes etc

C:4 Products Selling: This category, 'Products Selling', was developed by combing codings, 'School Exhibitions', 'Different Fair', 'Local Markets', and 'Selling by Parents'. Selling products is the only way to earn money. School authorities and parents played a big role achieve this objective. School authorities organise School Exhibitions for parents, guests and outsiders. Parents, Students and school authorities open stalls in public or governmental fairs such as Sabala Mela and RozgarMela, and book fairs to sell the products. The parents also sell products in the local market or local areas.

C:5 Using of Earn Money: Money of sold products or the category 'Using of Earn Money' is retrieved from the coding 'Earning Cash Money', 'Bank Transferring', 'Organizing a One-day Trip', and 'Buying Raw Materials'. EIDC gets the earned money through hand cash or bank transfer. Somewhere schools organise a trip for a day. Schools also buy raw materials to produce new products. Getting a few portions of the money as reinforcement makes them feel happy and increases their self-confidence.

C:6 Arrangement of Funds: 'NRI Funds', 'Higher authority's Fund', 'State Government Funds', & 'Central Government Funds', those codes make the category 'Arrangement of Funds'. Financial supports are important to all schools. Support from different sources, such as funds from any NRI person, Higher authority, central government, and state government is arranged.

C:7 Job Placements: This category was developed using the codes 'Office Clerk', 'Shopping Mall Staff', and 'Own Business'. A few EIDC got jobs as clerks in offices or units of their present schools and clerks in any shopping mall such as Pantaloons, Rangoli. A few numbers of EIDCs have their own business-like Xerox centers at home.

C:8Parent's Participations: 'Parent's Participations' is converted from these four codes 'Interested', 'Motivated', 'Lack of Awareness', and 'Lack of Involvement' Parental involvement is very important for empowering the EIDC. Parents were Interested & motivated but lacks in awareness and so as involvement. Active participation of both parents & EIDC is important.

C:9Trainer's Participations: In school, the trainers have an important role in empowering EIDC. So here, the category 'Trainer's Participations' are retrieved from those codes 'Energetic', 'Interested', and 'Feeling anger'. Maximum number of trainers had a special education degree and were energetic. Few trainers were impatient and handling EIDC aggressively. Lack of empathy may harm EIDC.

C:10Special Educator's Suggestions: From Special Educator's side few codes such as 'Wants Governmental Facilities', 'Focusing on Individuality', 'Necessities of Job Findings', 'Needs Awareness', and 'Parental Counseling' were formed. An initiative of the state or central government is a very important. Since Special children want special care, individual focus; Parents counseling, social awareness and their acceptance in public at large needs to of paramount importance.

The observations and related suggestions gathered in the study for empowerment of EIDC need to be addressed at all levels to witness a change in the lives of EIDC. The economic empowerment of EIDC and getting appreciation from policy point of view is not a new phenomenon but its implementation is yet too far to be a success. It is well known that Children with Intellectual disabilities are affected by their intelligence, but Educable Intellectually Disabled Children can live independently through basic education & proper vocational training at the school levels. More facilities from government, professional attitude of school authorities, more involvement from the parents, awareness in the society and their acceptance in the public at large can only bring job placement opportunities for EIDC. For this an effective Follow-up plan needs to be chalked out at the Govt level, school level and parents level.

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